

PECULIARITIES OF STUDYING BIOPHYSICS IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES

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Amidst the ever-evolving landscape of society and ongoing social shifts, the issue of nurturing full spiritual development within humanity and culture becomes particularly significant. Consequently, several pressing concerns emerge regarding the realm of education overall, especially higher education, as attitudes toward it undergo a transformation in perceived value.

Keywords: Biophysics, teaching, teaching methods, medicine, needs, laboratory, mechanics, acoustics, diffusion processes.

Higher education institutions, in alignment with the objective needs of societal development, aim to structure their operations within the framework of active reforms across the entire national education system. This entails recognizing the intrinsic value of each individual as a participant in educational and cognitive endeavors. Hence, the primary objective of the state's educational policy, as outlined in Uzbekistan's "On Education" law, is to foster conditions conducive to attaining high-quality education. This involves directing individuals toward the values, meanings, and motivations of learning, which are shaped by the enduring needs of individuals, society, and the state.

In medical universities, the first-year curriculum includes the study of "Medical and Biological Physics," a discipline with distinct characteristics that intersect with traditional physics coursework while also diverging significantly from it. For instance, the curriculum encompasses key areas such as biomechanics, which delves into the mechanical properties of living tissues and organs; hemodynamics, focusing on blood circulation through vessels; and cell biophysics, which explores the supramolecular structures within living cells, particularly membrane structures and subcellular particles. Additionally, the curriculum examines physical processes occurring in bodily tissues under the influence of currents and electromagnetic fields. This interdisciplinary approach not only enriches the study of medical biophysics but also underscores the importance of physics and mathematics in medical practice, fostering a materialistic understanding of living organisms and their physiological processes.

Despite the aforementioned aspects, physics instructors in medical schools encounter significant challenges in teaching this subject. Primarily, this is attributed to the minimal, and at times complete lack of, interest and engagement among medical students in physics studies, along with the weak motivational aspect of education. Moreover, the situation is exacerbated by the inadequate physical preparedness of students, which can be alarming due to their deficient foundational knowledge and skills not only in physics but also in mathematics. Consequently, physics instructors are compelled to explore a wide array of teaching methods and strategies to enhance students' cognitive engagement in the study of medical biophysics. It is crucial to cultivate students' interest in this subject, and this responsibility primarily rests on the physics teacher.

Currently, the teaching of academic disciplines, particularly at the university level, is conducted relatively independently, lacking sufficient integration of interconnected concepts. This approach leads students to perceive the studied disciplines as fragmented and disconnected. Integrating general educational principles with specialized education can enhance the effectiveness of the university learning process, necessitating close attention and thorough examination. Numerous works have been published on this issue. However, in the practical realm of teaching medical and biological physics, the outcomes of theoretical and practical research on continuity and interactivity are underutilized. Physics is fundamentally an experimental science, and without demonstrations, achieving a profound understanding of the subject is challenging. Unfortunately, organizing demonstration experiments can be difficult, and sometimes unfeasible, necessitating the use of alternative methods to illustrate physical phenomena and processes under study, such as virtual demonstrations.

Biophysics lectures delivered at the department are enriched with multimedia content, incorporating videos of experiments, animations, and illustrations of physical phenomena and processes. Comprehensive presentation materials have been curated for each lecture, covering various areas of biophysics, including mechanics, acoustics, diffusion processes in biological membranes, electrodynamics, medical electronics, optics, elements of quantum biophysics, ionizing radiation, and the basics of dosimetry.

A crucial component of biophysics education is the laboratory workshop, which fosters the development of students' practical skills. Through hands-on laboratory exercises, students learn to execute assigned tasks, analyze results, apply acquired experimental skills, and utilize physical and mathematical principles in research endeavors. During laboratory sessions, students explore assigned tasks, bridge theoretical concepts with practical applications, analyze outcomes, and draw conclusions. Proficiency in operating various equipment utilized in modern medicine is emphasized throughout the laboratory sessions.

Laboratory workshops are structured into introductory sessions, focusing on equipment familiarization and setup, and experimental sessions, where students tackle specific problem statements, conduct experiments, and analyze results. To facilitate effective learning, student groups are subdivided into smaller subgroups comprising 2-4 individuals. Students collaborate within these subgroups, engaging in measurements, calculations, and information exchange under the guidance of the instructor. Finally, the assessment and evaluation of laboratory work are conducted on an individual basis, ensuring each student's comprehension and proficiency in the subject matter.

In another workshop format, the experimental results obtained by each subgroup are documented in a table, and a collective graph is generated. This graph serves as the basis for identifying errors in the experiment, enabling a comprehensive analysis of the stages where mistakes occurred within each subgroup. Subsequently, any subgroup identified with errors repeats the experiment to rectify them. During the analysis of laboratory findings, the "brainstorming" method is employed, wherein all responses to a given question are considered valid. This approach facilitates the exploration of individual perspectives within the group, with the teacher posing questions to elicit student opinions and consensus on the subject matter. In this collaborative environment, every student's input is valued, and only correct responses are assessed, alleviating concerns about receiving unsatisfactory grades and enabling the teacher to gauge the level of comprehension following theoretical

instruction. All experimental outcomes are meticulously documented in report forms, a requisite element for honing practical skills, with results presented in tabular and graphical formats. The primary objective of studying biophysics for students pursuing a "General Medicine" track is to instill comprehensive knowledge and proficiency in mathematical and natural sciences, essential for mastering other academic disciplines and applying them autonomously in professional endeavors, as outlined in the competencies of the Federal State Educational Standard. To ensure the effective training of medical professionals, active and interactive educational methodologies are indispensable.

- Active learning involves dynamic interaction between teachers and students, collaboratively tackling tasks to foster independent problem-solving skills. This approach aims to cultivate the ability to comprehend and resolve challenges autonomously.
- Interactive learning, on the other hand, sees students engaging with both peers and educators to simulate scenarios and collectively address problems, fostering group-based problem-solving skills. In the teaching of biophysics at our department, diverse methodologies are employed to enhance educational quality and nurture students' independent thinking.
- Test tasks are utilized at the outset of the "biophysics" discipline to gauge students' foundational knowledge and for ongoing progress assessment. Each section of study concludes with a comprehensive test comprising theoretical inquiries and practical exercises, ranging from defining physical laws and quantities to qualitative and quantitative problem-solving tasks. This structured approach ensures systematic student engagement and active participation in the learning process, facilitating individual progress monitoring. While this teaching method undoubtedly places additional demands on teachers, particularly in task verification and preparation, it ultimately enables comprehensive student assessment and contributes to improved learning outcomes by semester's end.

Based on the aforementioned considerations, we have formulated a methodology for conducting physics practical sessions in a medical university. This approach emphasizes the activation of cognitive engagement among medical students, fostering heightened interest and participation in class activities, and recognizing, motivating, and rewarding the most capable and dedicated students.

In alignment with the new educational standards, students receive credits upon completing the course, rather than undergoing traditional examinations. This opens the possibility of automatic credit attainment, a concept that some educators may perceive as unjustified, given that students often harbor numerous questions about the course material while preparing for tests. However, the process of test preparation entails revisiting and consolidating the subject matter, contributing to its reinforcement and organization.

Despite differing opinions among teachers, the option for automatic credit acquisition serves as a compelling incentive for consistent and active engagement throughout the duration of the course. Moreover, considering physics as a non-core subject in a medical curriculum, the prospect of automatic credit attainment holds practical significance.

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